

Grain quality

Relation between rice grain quality and land preparation methods

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Several methods of rice land preparation are used in Pakistan depending on availability of irrigation water, soil type, and ease of preparation.

We studied the effect of land preparation methods on grain quality by comparing complete puddling (eight cultivations and eight plankings under 30 d wet conditions); partial puddling (four cultivations and four plankings under dry conditions, and four cultivations and four plankings under 10 d wet conditions); and dry land preparation (eight cultivations

Effect of land preparation methods on grain quality, 1988-90.^a

Quality attribute	Timing of N application		
	Complete puddling	Partial puddling	Dry land preparation
1000-grain weight (g)	19.1 a	18.8 ab	18.2 b
Total milled rice (%)	71.6 a	71.1 a	70.0 b
Head rice (%)	57.0 a	56.2 b	54.7 c
Cooked grain length (mm)	12.4 a	12.2 a	11.8 a
Bursting of cooked grains (%)	6.0 c	7.2 b	9.7 a
Protein content (%)	10.0 a	9.6 a	8.9 b
Amylose content (%)	29.3 a	3.7 a	29.5 a
Alkali spreading value	6.8 a	6.0 a	6.9 a
Gel consistency (mm)	54.0 a	50.0 a	43.0

^a Results were averaged for 1988-90. In a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

and three plankings under dry conditions followed by flooding and transplanting).

We transplanted a medium-grain variety KS282 on the same day of 1988, 1989, and 1990. The experiment was laid out in unreplicated 30- × 60-m plots. Recommended crop management practices were adopted.

Complete puddling produced the highest values for 1,000-grain weight, total and head rice recoveries, cooked

grain length, protein content, and gel consistency, followed by partial puddling and dry land preparation methods (see table). The reverse trend was observed in bursting of cooked grains. The effect of land preparation method on amylose content and alkali spreading value was nonsignificant. The complete puddling produced the highest quality grain followed by partial puddling and dry land preparation methods. □

Rice grain quality as influenced by split application of nitrogenous fertilizer

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We studied the effect of split N application on fine-grain strain 4048 during 1989 and 1990 dry seasons. Soil was loamy clay, with pH 8.0, E_Ce 1.95 dS/m, 0.067% N, 10 ppm available P, and 65 ppm available K. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications in a 4- × 9-m plot.

We applied a fertilizer dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. P and K were broadcast and incorporated into the soil during the last puddling. N was applied in two splits (half as basal, half 30 d after transplanting [DT]), or in three splits (one-third basal, at 30 DT, and at 60 DT).

Three splits of N fertilizer produced significantly higher 1,000-grain weight and head rice recovery, and less burst grain during cooking than two splits (see

Effect of split application of N fertilizer on grain quality, 1989 and 1990.^a

Quality characteristic	Timing of N application	
	Basal and 30 DT	Basal, 30, and 60 DT
1,000-grain weight (g)	18.3 b	19.0 a
Total milling recovery (%)	70.2 a	70.7 a
Head rice recovery (%)	48.3 b	53.7 a
Cooked grain length (mm)	14.5 a	15.1 a
Bursting of cooked grains (%)	8.0 a	6.0 b
Protein content (%)	8.7 a	9.0 a
Amylose content (%)	24.8 a	25.0 a
Gel consistency (mm)	61.0 b	64.0 a
Alkali spreading value	4.2 b	4.5 a

^a Results are averaged for 1989 and 1990. In a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

table). Values for gel consistency and alkali spreading were also significantly higher for the three splits but remained in

the same quality groups: soft gel consistency and intermediate gelatinization temperature. □

Pest resistance—diseases

A new symptom of tungro in rice

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We tested four accessions of *Oryza glaberrima* a West Africa cultivated rice, for resistance to tungro. The accessions—IRGC 100139, 100153, 102569, and 103437—all showed severe systemic necrosis, a new symptom of tungro infection, 2 or 3 wk after inoculation